

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

The Use of Academic Library Resources and Services by Undergraduate in Ibadan North Local Government of Nigeria

Awotola Uche Caroline¹ | Olowolagba Jamie Adewale²

¹² Adeniran Ogunsanya College of Education Oto, Ijanikin, Lagos.

Abstract: Libraries provide resources for knowledge acquisition, recreation, personal interests and inter-personal relationships for all categories of users. It enables the individual to obtain spiritual, inspirational, and recreational activities through reading, and therefore the opportunity of interacting with the society's wealth and accumulated knowledge. This study examined the undergraduate students' use of University library services and resources. It was affirmed the undergraduate utilized the University Libraries as learning centre. This was shown by the massive turn out to patronize the library services and resources weekly.

Keywords: Academic Library, Library Resources, Ibadan North Local Government.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'library' comes from 'liber' the latin word for "book", library has the collection of books and other informational materials made available to students for reading, studying and references (Akpan et al, 2018). The present age is called information age and it is merely not possible to keep track with improvement activities in the non-appearance of a reliable library and information system in a developing country. An effective library system is an essential requirement for research and development in every field of study. Scientists and researchers need to know about the information tools and resources available for better utilization of information. Failure to provide accurate and adequate information to the target groups may perhaps lead to defective results which will, in turn, hinder national development.

Roberson (2005) defines a library as an institution that manages the intellectual products that individual can gain access readily. Iyanda and Salawu (2006) on the other hand sees library as a building, an instructional and self-development centre, which operates as an integral part of the entire school environment. Also Ranganathan as quoted by Iyanda and Salawu (2006) describes library as a public institution or an establishment charged with the care of collection of books, the duty of making them accessible to those who require the use of them and the task of converting every person in its neighborhood into habitual library goers and readers of books.

The library enables the individual to obtain spiritual, inspirational, and recreational activity through reading, and therefore the opportunity of interacting with the society's wealth and accumulated knowledge. The library can be seen as an extension of education. Library services are needed to keep the skills that have been acquired through literacy classes alive by the provision of good literature. .

Libraries provide resources for knowledge acquisition, recreation, personal interests and inter-personal relationships for all categories of users. However in an academic environment, attention is basically focused on academic and non-academic staff, students and researchers. Today's libraries are repositories and access points for print, audio, and visual materials in numerous formats, including maps, prints, documents, microform (microform/microfiche), CDs, cassettes, videotapes, DVDs, videogames, e-books, audio books (microfilm/microfiche), and many other electronic resources.

Libraries often provide facilities to access electronic resources and the Internet. Modern libraries are increasingly being redefined as places to get unrestricted access to information in many formats and from many sources. They are extending services beyond the physical walls of a building, by providing material accessible by electronic means, and by providing the assistance of librarians in navigating and analyzing tremendous amounts of information with a variety of digital tools.

Because they serve such a diverse range of people, libraries maintain collections that can span the spectrum of human knowledge and opinions. Library collection include printed materials such as reference sources, novels, children's and young adult literatures, historical books, newspapers, and magazines. They usually also contained photographs, maps, art reproductions, sound and video recordings. In addition to print and non-print materials, there are computers CD-ROMs, and interconnections to information worldwide through the Internet.

Libraries are established in educational institutions to meet the information needs of users – students and staff. These libraries include libraries in Universities, polytechnics, Colleges of Education and secondary/primary schools. The roles of these libraries are similar and this is to effectively support the institutions to attain the key functions of teaching, learning and research services. These institutions are responsible for the creation of middle and higher level manpower for national development. The extent to which these institutions are able to effectively accomplish this task depends largely on how well the libraries are stocked with relevant information resources.

According to Akpan and Akpan (2018) the university library is the principal instrument of the university in the conservation of recorded knowledge. Proper fulfillment of this role provides a sound basis for the transmission and advancement of knowledge. However, every university library, no matter the size is established to render service to its users. The library has to collect materials, published and unpublished, print and non-print, in some depth and globally in all the fields of knowledge not necessarily in those offered in its institution.

According to Aguolu and Aguolu (2002) the basic functions of any university is to conserve the existing knowledge, to transmit knowledge through teaching and to create new knowledge through research. The university library provides university the needed information resources, which aids to extend the frontier of knowledge. It has the function of supporting teaching, learning and research activities that go on in the various institutions. In performing the function university libraries stock thousands of information resources such as books, journals and non-books resources and provide access to them. However, the importance of well-stocked university libraries cannot be overemphasized; they contribute to the quality of the university as centers of learning and research. Thus the university library has been regarded as “the heart” of the unit – the most indispensable agency or unit for teaching, learning and research. Nwalo (2002) summarizes the basic materials needed in most institutional libraries, as:

- books relating to a specific subject area and important books in subject field not included in the curriculum;
- books for voluntary and recreational reading.
- professional and research materials for both the faculty and students who requires them.
- periodicals and newspapers in foreign language, current issues, bound volume and those on microfilm, micro cards, and other electronic resources;.
- pamphlets and paper clippings.
- audio-visual materials including picture films, slides, filmstrips, transparencies, music, photography, records, tape and wire recordings, maps and globes.
- programmes materials.
- government publications.
- archival materials pertaining to the institutions.
- equipment for the use of these materials such as micro-readers, listening and viewing equipment.

Apparently, the effectiveness of a library is perceived by the amount of information resources, facilities put in to guarantee this. This become imperative because library exists to serve the users and their views and opinions are very important in ranking the performance of the library (Akinwumi, 1986; Adedibu and Adio, 1997). According to Oyewusi and Oyeboade (2009) the primary purpose of university libraries is to support teaching, learning and research in ways consistent with, and supportive of the institution's mission and goals. In addition, library resources and services should be sufficient in quality, depth, diversity and currency to support the institution curriculum. As a result of this, university libraries are often considered as the most important resource centre of an academic institution.

Self (1990) too, argued that providing students with access to an expanded collection would increase their use of the library. Udoh (1986) observed that libraries exhibit inadequacies in personnel, and funding. These facts were supported by Adesola (1991) who claimed that the under-funding resulted from the scarcity of foreign exchange. The under-funding was claimed other researchers (Fagbeja, 1993; Fakoya, 2002) to have adverse effects on the quality of libraries in the country. As such, learning tends to be at the memory level of intelligence (Obinna, 2004; Ifueko, 2005).

Merrill (2003) related library resources to students' learning outcomes and found that the use of library resources were associated significantly with better learning outcomes. Crossley and Murby (1994) too, remarked that the inadequacy of relevant books in school libraries could contribute markedly to low levels of outcomes. This finding agreed with the findings made by Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (2004) and the National Literacy Trust's (2004).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Preliminary observation has shown that most students run away from making use of the libraries. Libraries are said to be institutions that support learning activities in all sphere of education. Could it therefore be that this observed trend is as a result of how the students perceive or view the library or could there be other factors responsible for this behavior?

There are different categories of users that make use of university libraries, among these are the undergraduate, postgraduate students, lecturers and researchers. However, it is observed that this category of people rarely visit the library and therefore it is often difficult to assess if

the library is meeting their needs as the aim of any good library is to satisfy all its users and thereby justify its existence. The aim of the study therefore, is to find out how undergraduates perceive the services render and resources in University libraries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of library and its importance

A library is regarded as a place where knowledge is stored and its main objective is to meet the needs of the users. The importance of this repository of knowledge called library, shows the necessity of literature review in the academic world. Olorunsaye (2003) quoted Opee (1985) who described literature review as “gathering” of information about how other have approached or dealt with similarly problems”. Literature review is therefore a means to discovering what has been previously done on the subject and the methodology that has been applied. It must then be noted that, unless excellent libraries are available, it would not be possible to make references to need literature for review. .

A lot of studies have been carried out on library use. This is so because it is the users that make the library and its services come alive. A library that is not used is as good as dead as it cannot justify its existence. It is therefore the use to which the library is put that infuses life into its resources and services; hence, use and user studies cannot outlive their usefulness.

Akinade (2000) observed that the expectations of people are high when sourcing and retrieving information and when such information needs are not met, frustration usually set in and this may drive the users away from the library. Akande (2003) therefore noted that the use of library resources is uppermost in the minds of the university libraries as this will enable the management know how best they can serve their users. Users’ study is thus regarded as a veritable tool for the assessment of libraries and their services (Tsafe, 2004).

However, literature has revealed that information availability does not mean accessibility and utilization; therefore, university libraries have to market their resources and services to attract users. Osinulu (1998) also confirmed in her study that low use of the library is due to lack of awareness on the part of users. Ozoemelem (2009), on the other hand, stated that informed library users know that libraries have resources that are more comprehensive and scholarly than most websites provide but the problem is that these resources they are not straightforward like that on the webs. Though users use the library for different purposes, Oyesiku and Oduwole (2004) study on the use of academic library revealed that students use the library mostly during examinations period. In a study conducted by Igun and Adogbeji (2007) among the postgraduate students, majority of the students claimed that their main purpose of using the library is to update their knowledge and skills. It is therefore, essential to know the needs and opinions of the users in order to satisfy them. In buttressing this, Bassey (2006) posited that satisfying the request of users implies providing the actual information or services that will meet their needs.

Among many users of the university library are the postgraduate students. This class of students are regarded as ‘matured students’ because they have pass through the undergraduate stage and are now facing a higher level of academic studies. Rasul and Singh (2010) observed that there are scanty literatures on the needs of the postgraduate students, yet they form a significant group of researchers in a university. Furthermore, they noted that how the postgraduate students perceive the role of their university library matters a lot. This is very important because the nature of postgraduate study demands that students must do a lot of

independent studies on their own. The use of library resources and services is thus indispensable to the postgraduate students in order to achieve their academic objective. As a result, Olofinsawe and Oyeniyi (2010) affirmed that academic libraries have to build strong collection of information resources in physical and digital format to cater for knowledge requirements of their users.

According to Forrest (2009), the library's success should be measured not in terms of what it has (inputs) but of what it does, the activities it supports, its outputs for example circulation transactions, reference questions answered, classes taught and students enrolled. This also explains the significant role of the library staff, as they have to treat the users as important guests and in that way they will contribute to their satisfaction. "The library's success is measured by what happens as a result of those activities and encounters, the impacts or outcomes (for example fostering student learning success, supporting faculty productivity, enhancing institutional reputation). If we can frame experiences for our students, faculty and visitors – our guests – that linger in their memory long after they have left our libraries and our campuses, we will continue to remain central to the academic enterprise" (Forrest, 2009).

According to Nwalo (2003), a library is primarily set up to acquire, organize, store and make accessible to the users, within the quickest possible time all forms of information materials which they require. The systematic acquisition, organization and dissemination at books not mere label distinguishes a library from either a reading room or store house at books.

UNDERGRADUATES USE OF ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

There have been many literature of utilization of resources and services such as Ogbomo and Adomi, (2003), Turtle, (2005) Haruna, (2004) and Swarna, (2004) among others. In a study carried out by Hussain and Kumar, (2013) on utilization of information resources and service of the postgraduate students, majority of the users frequently visit the library almost daily and it was further found that books, newspapers and periodicals are the most used by user. In addition, in a study on students and faculty use of academic libraries in Nigeria, Okly, (2000) found that respondents used books more than other materials and that they browsed the shelves to locate these materials. In line with findings, Ugah,(2007) further found out that textbooks account for most library visit. Base on the gap in literatures on the extent of utilization of the library resources for effective research output among postgraduate students of Babcock University it becomes critical to understudy this population of postgraduate students.

Akinbode (2002) opined that it is the responsibility of the library to render certain services to users so as to make maximum use of library materials. Services to be rendered to users include instruction on the use of the library, issuance of guide to the library and the library regulations to readers, provision of general and specific information, assistance on location of documents; reservation of documents for the benefit of readers.

Omoniwa (1986) explained that library services is not that of propaganda but that of generating, collecting synthesizing and disseminating up-to-date, accurate, unbiased and relevant information available in books, periodicals, bulletins, guides, abstracts, indexes, bibliographies and non-book format which can be stored and retrieved whenever needed. This is to say that it is the primary responsibility of the library to identify the information needs of its target audience, collate the necessary available data and feed the analyzed information back to it users. According to Ifidon (1999), university library is a service organization with the primary obligation to provide the bibliographic resources in fulfillment of university mission.

Adegun (2015) conducted a research on Effectiveness of Library Service and Resources in an African University and observed that if library service and resources are adequate and readily available, it would result to increase in use. Also if there is improvement in the response to users' needs, the end result will thus be an increase in the library's role in the pursuit of user's educational goals, research and needs. In developing nations like Nigeria, where book buying is a luxury because of the prohibitive cost and limited book markets, it becomes a matter of priority for the library to provide effective service and resources to its numerous users. The library should not only build adequate and balanced functional resources, but also provide access to the resources. The more detailed the assistance given, the more humbly it is given, the more certain will be the satisfaction of the user and an increase in library use. In providing effective service and resources in university libraries, the librarian should cater for varying level of users within and outside the university. Library resources need to be used adequately in order to justify the huge amount invested in them.

UNDERGRADUATE REASONS FOR USING THE LIBRARY

Universities are to generate new knowledge and also encourage transferred and adopted of this new innovation. Since this requires an atmosphere of research, libraries are left with no options or choice than to provide access to relevant information resources by applying this to enable quick access, integrate and repackage information for the end user that will capacitate and enrich higher educational institutions means of conducting research.

Basically, library resources are materials that users consult in making decisions and also for problem-solving. These sources could be primary or secondary sources. Ojedokun (2007) noted that primary sources are uninterpreted, first hand materials such as records and raw data. In other words, library sources are sources that users make use of from time to time in order to meet their information needs. These library resources could also refer to audiovisual materials, such as Audio CD and CDROM for data storage which do not depend solely on reading to get their meanings but they convey relevant information.

Many scholars have written on utilization of resources and services such as Ogbomo and Adomi, (2003), Turtle, (2005) Haruna, (2004) and Swarna, (2004) among others. In a study carried out by Hussain and Kumar, (2013) on utilization of information resources and service of the postgraduate students, majority of the users frequently visit the library almost daily and it was further found that books, newspapers and periodicals are the most used by user. In addition, in a study on students and faculty use of academic libraries in Nigeria, Okly,(2000) found that respondents used books more than other materials and that they browsed the shelves to locate these materials. In line with findings, Ugah, (2007) further found out that textbooks account for most library visit.

Studies carried out Oluwatobi, Ehioghae, Aluko-Arowole and Onasote (2014) revealed that the most frequently used library materials is the online database and this is followed by Dictionaries, books, encyclopedia which are used daily, while the least is use material is CD-ROM database. In other words, undergraduates utilize online database of the university and dictionaries often to enhance their research study than any other information resources available in the library. Hussain and Kumar, (2013) also found that books, newspapers and periodicals are the most used by undergraduate students sampled in their studies. This finding also correlates with Ugai (2001) who found out that textbooks account for most library visits.

Akinbode (2002) opined that it is the responsibility of the library to render certain

services to users so as to make maximum use of library materials. Services to be rendered to users include instruction on the use of the library, issuance of guide to the library and the library regulations to readers, provision of general and specific information, assistance on location of documents; reservation of documents for the benefit of readers.

Omoniwa (1986) explained that library services is not that of propaganda but that of generating, collecting synthesizing and disseminating up-to-date, accurate, unbiased and relevant information available in books, periodicals, bulletins, guides, abstracts, indexes, bibliographies and non-book format which can be stored and retrieved whenever needed. This is to say that it is the primary responsibility of the library to identify the information needs of its target audience, collate the necessary available data and feed the analyzed information back to it users. According to Ifidon (1999), university library is a service organization with the primary obligation to provide the bibliographic resources in fulfillment of university mission.

INFORMATION RESOURCES AVAILABLE IN MOST ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

UNESCO as quoted in IFLA publication (1979) defined the library as any organized collection of printed books and periodicals of any other graphic and audio visual materials and the services of the staff to provide such materials as are required to meet the information, research educational or recreational needs of its user. Library resources found in developed countries support teaching and learning functions by facilitating research and scholarship of students and lecturers but this is not the situation in most developing countries because the libraries are struggling to survive due to financial constraints. Accessing Nigerian libraries against UNESCO 1979 definition could be unexplainable to some minds but some of our libraries do not have adequate books, periodicals and audio visuals been acquired into the libraries not to talk of a 2007 definition of UNESCO which may include electronic/digital resources. The question then is “how many academic libraries in Nigeria fits into this definition of a library as defined by UNESCO?” “Can Nigerian university libraries boast of adequate collection of books, periodicals and electronic resources to meet with the needs of library users?” “Can Nigerian university libraries meet the information, research, educational and recreational needs of Nigerian students and researchers?”

These are pertinent questions that need to be answered in order to know the current state of library resources in Nigeria. Although university libraries in Nigeria are in a better shape in terms of resources (both printed and electronic) compared to public libraries. However, librarians in Nigeria are hard working people putting in place libraries that users would access and use despite the few resources placed at their disposal. These problems could be minimized when library administrators are more vigorous in lobbying university administrators to see the importance of the library and to release more funds. However, there is little empirical data about how electronic/digital resources are being used by Nigerian undergraduates bearing in mind that most universities in Nigeria have not fully digitized their library resources.

Libraries from time immemorial have been essential constituents of scholastic enterprise and have been established alongside with academic institutions. The library is the centre-point around which academic activities revolve. Academic libraries have the aim of supporting activities like teaching learning, research and leisure (Abiolu, 2010). This means that they are saddled with the responsibility of provision of information resources and information dissemination within the academic set-up. This responsibility is designed to make universities perform their roles effectively and efficiently in order to attain the objectives and

aims for which they are established (Tsafo, 2004). The relationship between academic libraries and institutions of higher learning is symbolic (Ijatuyi, 1991). More often than not, academic libraries have been equated to what the heart is to the physical body.

Information resource, as a concept, has been interchangeably used for information materials, information carriers, or learning resources. Aina (2004) while describing the range of information carriers stresses that information required by the user appears in a variety of formats such as books, serials, maps, compact disc, and the likes. Igben (1993) believes that any library or information service is in the business of providing services to its user community. It is however observed, that dissemination of knowledge being the overall goal of the library can be evaluated in terms of relationships between potential information contained in the information carriers in the library collection and the degree of satisfaction of the patron's needs (Akinpelu, 1995). Umunakwe (1988) as quoted by Sado and Ibeun (2006) avers that the yardstick to measure any library is the quality of its collection, adding that any money spent on a standard collection is money wisely spent. The writers reveal from the findings that books and journals in the libraries are grossly inadequate in number and volume compared to the year of establishment to these libraries.

Library resources, according to the Dictionary for Library and Information science (1997) refer to all the items purchased by a library or library system to satisfy the information needs of its users, including books and non-book or rather called print and non-print resources such as newspapers and periodicals, reference materials, music scores, maps, microforms, and non prints media, as distinct from equipment supplies." Supporting this Aina (2004) posited that the collections of libraries normally include books, journals, gazetteers, pamphlets, audio-visual materials, government documents and serials. Some of them provide archives of literature, reports of federal, state and local government councils. However, for learning to be effective, teaching and research in the university, the library information resources must be relevant, current and in different formats print and non-print such as textbooks ,journals, magazines, indexes and abstracts, encyclopaedia, thesis and dissertations, microforms and electronic databases, publications of international organizations. Inadequacy of information resources, according to Okanla, (2012) affects the academic performance negatively. Gbaje, (2007) reveals that the inability of a library to stock relevant books and literature has a great implication on the activities of academic institutions. According to Ajiboro, (2008) the decline in information resources can result to ineffective use of libraries.

The library stock as defined by Elatouri (1992) is an organized collection of books and non – book media, especially collected to support the educational program of the school. Where there is adequate library stock, students will develop the habit of reading both for pleasure and for the purpose of gathering information for themselves. Adebimpe and Adeniran (2001) maintain that it is not out of place to say that the establishment of school libraries has a positive correlation with educational quality at school levels. Students learn easily when they are exposed to good learning resources materials and become more skilful in finding solution to problems. The library stock will develop and play its full role only if the college authorities and lecturers have a sincere believe that it is important to teaching and learning process.

Edoka (2000) however stated that libraries often provide public facilities for access to their electronic resources and the Internet Modern libraries are increasingly being redefined as places to get unrestricted access to information in many formats and from many sources. They are extending services beyond the physical walls of a building, by providing material accessible

by electronic means, and by providing the assistance of librarians in navigating and analysing very large amounts of information with a variety of digital tools.

Andaleeb and Simmons (2004) opined that library resources are critical to user education, submitting that no library can satisfy all its' users all the time. They further posit that some libraries have very limited resources and clearly unable to satisfy their user whereas others are large in size, have substantial holdings and can provide users with whatever they want will achieve high productivity of user satisfaction. Obviously the availability of resources can have a significant influence on user satisfaction.

Edoka (2000) opines that in general the function of academic libraries are to provide information materials required for the academic programs of the parent institution and also provide information resources in consonance with the needs of the faculty and students. The objectives of university can only be achieved by the selection and acquisition of relevant materials that are built around the course offered in the institutions. The acquisition of just any material is not enough. The librarian has to know whether the right materials are acquired and used this is usually achieved through systematic evaluation (Edoka and Okafor 2002).

The quantity and quality of information materials are fundamental to the survival of a library or information centre and to its parent body. In this regard, Nwalo (2000) notes that availability of relevant information materials is the hallmark of a library while Oyelude (2004) observes that it is one of the good qualities of a library. This is why academic libraries acquire and organize both print and electronic information resources for information materials for their users. Alternatively, however, as she opines, students and staff of tertiary institutions use information and communication technologies to retrieve current information electronically which is another form of information resources.

Yusuf (2001) reports that availability of adequate resources especially books and other related materials *is sine qua-non* for the existence of every academic library. Therefore, academic libraries should continue to struggle to acquire and organize relevant printed and other forms of recorded knowledge for the benefit of the community. Institutions of higher learning according to Egwin (2006) are established primarily to discharge the tripartite functions of teaching, research and community development. He further adduces that success in the execution of these responsibilities depends on a number of factors. One of the factors relevant in this regard is the availability of a carefully selected and organized collection of books, information and learning materials.

THE SERVICES RENDERED IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

The primary purpose of any library is to provide the information needs of its users. Likewise, all authorized users of academic and research libraries have a right to expect library services that commensurate with their needs, provided by competent librarians and founded on adequate collections which are easily available and accessible.

In the academic community, libraries are vital not only to continuing education and self-development, but also to research activities. They are indispensable because they are the nerve centre of all teaching, learning and research activities in a university. The fact that academic libraries occupy a paramount place in the life of their parent institutions has widely been discussed in many library literatures. Aloh (1988) described university libraries as the heart of the society, the only effective repository of racial memory.

Libraries in universities are established to help in achieving their primary objectives.

According to Nok (2006), university libraries have derived their objectives to include provision of materials for undergraduate instruction, term papers and projects, support of faculty, external and collaborative research, personal development, leisure and cooperation with other academic libraries with the view to developing a network of academic library resources that are at the disposal of all scholars. Therefore, services provided by the academic libraries must be planned in relation to the other faculties in the community they serve.

The quality and effectiveness of academic libraries is connected with services, products, as well as staff, facilities and space (Pindlowa, 2002). Ugah (2011) is also of the opinion that quality in the content of a library is often treated as the quality of service and the quality of service which also affects the effectiveness of the library is important for each library to survive.

Suleiman (2012) carried out a study on user education programs in academic libraries. The findings of the study revealed that users are in favor of various programs due to their adaptability, online public access catalogue, and easy access to several sources of information. For library services to keep pace with the needs of students, library should increase number of employees' expert and skillful librarians who can provide user education programs.

Yu (2003) explored how Taiwanese college and technical institution libraries familiarize user with library facilities and information resources. The most common programs are a basic introduction to library services, OPAC instruction, searching tools, internet instruction, CD-ROMs, databases and electronic journals, and audio and video materials.

Oyesola, (1984) studied on the problems facing the library in increasing students' ability to locate materials they need, extend their knowledge of useful library tools, encourage learners to make extensive use of the library and to give Student's Perceptions of Library Services in Ekiti State University them rudimentary knowledge of appropriate study methods. One of the objectives of user education program is to enable students to patronize libraries for their academic activities.

Clarcke (1999) revealed the growth of user education within the context of arguments for and against it. Library orientation tours and different approaches to them are described, as well as the development of undergraduate and postgraduate programs of user education.

Muogilim, (1986) found the lack of ability of the students to exploit library facilities after taking a course in the use of library. The conclusion of his findings shows that students were allowed few connections with the library and its staff during the orientation program. Also, they were overloaded with so much information within such a short period of time that the chances of retention and internationalization of the avalanche of new information is quite slim. He concludes that high enrolment with inadequate physical facilities made effective work difficult.

PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS BASE ON DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Table 4.1: Distribution of Respondents base on Gender

Gender	Number	Percentage (%)
Male	60	60.0
Female	40	40.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4.1. shows gender distribution of respondents, results from the study revealed that

there are more males (60.0%) than females (40.0%) students among the respondents. It is often assume that men use library resources than their female counterparts especially services and resources.

Table 4.2: Distribution of Respondents base on Age

Age	Number	Percentage (%)
12 to 16 years	30	30.0
17 to 21 years	38	38.0
27 to 31 years	32	32.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4.2 shows there are more students within the age range of 17 to 21 years (38.0%) of the total respondents while (32.0%) expressed that they were 27 to 31 years and (30.0%) were between 12 to 16 years. The implication here is that Ekiti state University students are in their acute years if they are still between 17 and 21 years.

Table 4.3: Distribution of Respondents base on Religion

Religion	Number	Percentage (%)
Christianity	57	57.0
Islam	38	38.0
Others Religion	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4.3 shows the religious distribution of respondents, results from the study revealed that there are more Christianity (57.0%) than Islam (38.0%) students and others religion of (5.0%) among the respondents, while . It is often assume that Christian use library resources than Islam and others religion believers.

Table 4.4: Distribution of Respondents base on Discipline

Discipline	Number	Percentage (%)
Electrical Engineering	7	7.0
Fishies and Agriculture	7	7.0
Public Administration	8	8.0
Accounting	8	8.0
Civil Engineering	6	6.0
Linguistic & Nigeria Languages	7	7.0
Psychology	8	8.0
Biochemistry	5	5.0
Economics	6	6.0
Genetics	6	6.0
History & International Studies	6	6.0
Geology	6	6.0

Microbiology	5	5.0
Botany	5	5.0
Physical Education	5	5.0
LARIS	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Findings from the study are presented base on Discipline. The findings showed that majority of the undergraduate students were from Public Administration, Accounting, Psychology, (8.0%), Electrical Engineering, Fisheries and Agriculture, Linquistic & Nigeria Languages (7.0%), Economics, Genetics History & International Studies , Geology Civil Engineering, (6.0%), Biochemstry Microbiology, Botany, Physical Education and LARIS (5.0%)

Table 4.5: Distribution of Respondents base on Level

Level	Number	Percentage (%)
100	29	29.0
200	27	27.0
300	33	33.0
400	11	11.0
Total	100	100.0

The information of the respondents reveals the level of respondents, results from the study revealed that there are more 33.0% 300 level students, 100 level was 29.0%, 200 level, was 27.0% and 400 level was 11.0% respectively. It is was implies that 300 level has high percentage.

4.2 Answer to research questions

Research Question One: What is the level of undergraduate students use of academic library?

Table 4.6: Respondents use of academic library

Use of the academic Library	Number	Percentage (%)
Daily	25	25.0
Weekly	44	44.0
Monthly	6	6.0
Occasionally	25	25.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4.6 shows the level of undergraduate students use of academic library, results from the study revealed that weekly was (44%) daily and occasionally was 25% and Monthly was 6% among the respondents.. This implies that the undergraduate students used the academic library weekly.

Research Question Two: For what purpose do undergraduate students make use of school academic library resources?

Table 4.7: Respondents purpose for using the academic library

S/ N	Items	Yes (%)	No (%)	Total (%)	Mea n	SD	Rank
1.	For assignment	77.0	23.0	100.0	.77	.423	1 st
2.	For examination	49.0	51.0	100.0	.49	.502	3 rd
3.	For reading magazines and newspapers	69.0	31.0	100.0.	.69	.465	2 nd
4.	For Leisure and recreation	40.0	60.0	100.0	.40	.492	4 th
5.	Other purposes	40.0	60.0	100.0	.40	.492	5 th

Table 4.7 presented results on the undergraduate purpose of using the academic library resources. The table shows that most of the respondents 77.0%, 69.0%, indicated they use the library for assignment and for reading magazines and newspapers while negative response were 60.0%, and 51.0% for examination and for leisure and recreation and others purposes. It could be inferred that the undergraduate students majorly use the academic library for assignment and reading of magazines and newspapers.

Research Question Three: What are the type of information resources use most by undergraduate students?

Table 4.8: Type of information resources use most by respondents

Key: Very Readily Available(VRA), Readily Available(RA), Not Readily Available(NRA), Not Available (NA)

S/N	Items	VRA%	RA %	NRA %	NA %	Mean	SD	Rank
1.	Dictionary	73.0	25.0	2.0	0.0	3.71	.498	1
2.	Encyclopedia	48.0	46.0	6.0	0.0	3.42	.606	2
3.	Internet facilities	52.0	19.0	24.0	5.0	3.18	.968	16
4.	Abstracts	33.0	56.0	11.0	0.0	3.22	.629	4
5.	Year books	40.0	42.0	16.0	2.0	3.20	.778	10
6.	Atlases	30.0	57.0	11.0	2.0	3.15	.687	5
7.	Gazettes	29.0	52.0	11.0	8.0	3.02	.853	11
8.	CD-ROM	33.0	48.0	15.0	4.0	3.10	.798	12
9.	Computer/Printers	44.0	40.0	8.0	8.0	3.20	.899	7
10.	Gazetteers	30.0	49.0	7.0	14.0	2.95	.968	15
11.	Journals	43.0	47.0	8.0	2.0	3.31	.706	3
12.	Almanacs	38.0	43.0	15.0	4.0	3.15	.821	13
13	Online Public access catalogue	39.0	47.0	11.0	3.0	3.22	.760	6
14	Maps	47.0	33.0	18.0	2.0	3.25	.821	14
15	Law reports	39.0	44.0	6.0	11.0	3.11	.942	8

16	Books	55.0	27.0	16.0	2.0	3.35	.841	9
----	-------	------	------	------	-----	------	------	---

Table 4.8 presented results on the type of information resources use most by undergraduate students. The table shows that most of the respondents 98.0%, 94.0%, 90.0%, 89.0%, 87.0%, 86.0%, 84.0%, 83.0%, 82.0%, 81.0% and 79.0% indicated the type of information resources use most by undergraduate students which include Dictionary, Encyclopedia, Journals, Abstracts, Atlases, Online Public access catalogue, Computer/Printers, Law reports, Books, Yearbooks, Gazettes, CD-ROM, Almanacs, Maps, Gazetteers, Internet facilities. Thus, it could be inferred that the following resources were types of information resources use mostly by undergraduate students - Dictionary, Encyclopedia, and Journals,

Research Question Four: What is the level of services rendered in academic library to undergraduate students?

Table 4.9: The level of services rendered in academic library

Key: Very Readily Available(VRA), Readily Available(RA), Not Readily Available(NRA), Not Available (NA)

S/ N	Items	VRA %	RA%	NRA %	NA %	Mea n	SD	Rank
1.	Selective Dissemination Information (SDI)	32.0	58.0	6.0	4.0	3.18	.716	1 90
2.	Inter library loan/Cooperation	19.0	58.0	18.0	5.0	2.91	.753	5 77
3.	Current Awareness Services(CAS)	35.0	36.0	29.0	0.0	3.06	.802	9 71
4.	Indexing & Abstracting services	15.0	55.0	26.0	4.0	2.81	.734	10 70
5.	Answering of Users' queries	19.0	56.0	18.0	7.0	2.87	.800	6 75
6.	User education i.e teaching users how best to exploit library resources	26.0	44.0	18.0	12.0	2.84	.950	11 70
7.	Library display and publicity	43.0	32.0	18.0	7.0	3.11	.942	7 75
8.	Internet facilities	46.0	35.0	15.0	4.0	3.23	.851	3 81
9.	Photocopying services	34.0	36.0	9.0	21.0	2.83	1.12 0	12 70
10.	Reference services	42.0	41.0	11.0	6.0	3.19	.861	2 83
11.	E-mail services	35.0	43.0	15.0	7.0	3.06	.886	4 78
12.	Telephone services	28.0	38.0	23.0	11.0	2.83	.965	13 66
13.	Online public access catalogue(OPAC)	36.0	36.0	28.0	0.0	3.08	.800	8 72

Table 4.9 shows the level of services rendered in academic library, The table reveals the services include Selective Dissemination Information (SDI), Reference services, Internet

facilities, E-mail services, Interlibrary loan/Cooperation, Answering of Users' queries, Library display and publicity, Online public access catalogue (OPAC), Current Awareness Services (CAS), Indexing & Abstracting services, User education i.e. teaching users how best to use the library resources, photocopying services and telephone services respectively with the following percentages: 90.0%, 83.0%, 81.0%, 78.0%, 77.0%, 75.0%, 72.0%, 71.0%, 70.0%, and 66.0% respectively. From the result it implies that Selective Dissemination of Information was rank first, followed by reference services which was second and thirdly Internet services.

Research Question Six: What are the problems encountered by undergraduates in using the Library?

Table 4.11: The problems encountered by undergraduates in using the Library

S/ N	Items	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Total %	Mean	SD	Rank
1.	In adequate library funding	70.0	30.0	100.0	3.02	.995	4
2.	Poor library staff/User relationship	71.0	29.0	100.0	3.08	.884	2
3.	In adequate reference sources	72.0	28.0	100.0	3.09	.898	1
4.	Erratic power supply	56.0	44.0	100.0	2.66	1.056	6
5.	Lack of current and relevant materials	71.0	29.0	100.0	3.05	.796	3
6.	Inadequate reading space	69.0	31.0	100.0	2.88	.902	5
7.	Lack of ICT resources (Internet)	37.0	63.0	100.0	2.61	.852	8
8.	Inadequate staff strength	62.0	38.0	100.0	2.62	.488	7

Table 4.11 shows the problem encountered by undergraduate students in using the academic library. Majority 72% indicated inadequate reference sources, while 28% disagreed. Again, 71% indicated poor library staff/user relationship and lack of current and relevant materials, while 29% disagreed respectively. Also, 70% indicated inadequate library funding while 30% disagreed. Similarly, 69% indicated inadequate reading space, while 31% disagreed. Others indicated erratic power supply 56%, inadequate staff strength 62% and lack of ICT resources (Internet) 37%. However, majority of the respondents 63% indicated that the ICT resources (Internet) were not a problem in the library.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the undergraduate students' perception of University library services and resources. It was affirmed the undergraduate perceived the University Library as learning centre. This was shown by the massive turn out to patronize the library services and resources weekly. Adegun (2015) conducted a research on Effectiveness of Library Service and Resources in an African University and observed that if library service and resources are adequate and readily available, it would result to increase in use. Akinade (2000) observed that

the expectations of people are high when sourcing and retrieving information and when such information needs are not met, frustration usually set in and this may drive the users away from the library.

The study equally revealed the undergraduates purpose of using University Library and resources. The study shows they use the library for various reasons such as for assignment, reading magazines and newspapers, reading for examination and for leisure and recreation activities. From the results it was inferred that the undergraduate students majorly use the academic library for assignment and reading of magazines and newspapers. This findings agreed with Oyesiku and Oduwole (2004) study on the use of academic library which revealed that students use the library mostly during examinations period. In a study conducted by Igun and Adogbeji (2007) among the undergraduate students, majority of the students claimed that their main purpose of using the library is to update their knowledge and skills.

The study affirmed type of information resources mostly used by undergraduate students in State University Library. The major information resources often used by undergraduate in University Library were Dictionary, Encyclopedia, Journals, Abstracts, Atlases, Online Public access catalogue, Computer/Printers, Law reports, Books, Yearbooks, Gazettes, CD-ROM, Almanacs, Maps, Gazetteers, Internet facilities. This findings is in line with Hussain and Kumar, (2013) who asserted that books, newspapers and periodicals are the most used by undergraduate students. Supporting this Aina (2004) posited that the collections of libraries normally include books, journals, gazetteers, pamphlets, audio-visual materials, government documents and serials.

The study also examined the level of services rendered in University Library to undergraduate's students. The results reveals the services include Selective Dissemination Information (SDI), Reference services, Internet facilities, E-mail services, Interlibrary loan/Cooperation, Answering of Users' queries, Library display and publicity, Online public access catalogue (OPAC), Current Awareness Services (CAS), Indexing & Abstracting services, User education i.e. teaching users how best to use the library resources, photocopying services and telephone services respectively.

The perception of the undergraduate students of the Ekiti State University Library shows that the resources were useful academic programme and up-to-date. The library was also assessed by undergraduates as a place for serious academic activities as well as the environment being conducive for learning and reading.

Finally, the problem encountered by undergraduate students in using the University Library were that the library has inadequate reference sources, poor library staff/user relationship and lack of current and relevant materials. Others includes poor funding, erratic power supply and poor ICT connectivity which made browsing the Internet an up-hill task. This collaborate Hanif, *et.al* (1997) who reported that there was inadequacy of recent publications and current journals. Besides, the information needs of the undergraduate were not adequately met by the existing library resources in most academic libraries.

The major findings of the study are as follows:

1. The undergraduate students make use of the academic library weekly.
2. They used the academic library to do their assignment, read magazines and newspapers, and also to prepare themselves for examination as well as for leisure and recreational activities and others purposes.

3. The type of information resources use mostly by undergraduate students in the library include Dictionary, Encyclopedia and Journals..
4. Services rendered to undergraduate students in the library includes Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI), Reference services. Internet services, E-mail services and Interlibrary loan.
5. Undergraduates perceived the academic library services and resources as useful and up-to-date, it enhances academic progress, conducive for serious academic activities, learning/reading. Above all, the librarians were friendly and knowledgeable, however, they lack good interpersonal relationship.
6. The problem encountered by undergraduate students in using the academic library includes inadequate reference sources, poor library staff/user relationship and lack of current and relevant materials, inadequate library funding, inadequate reading space, and erratic power supply.

CONCLUSION

The study examines the use of university library services and resources. The present age is called information age and it is merely not possible to keep track with improvement activities in the absence of a reliable library and information system in a developing country like ours. An effective library system is an essential requirement for research and development in every field of study. The study established the undergraduate students perceived the University library services and resources as useful and up-to-date, enhances academic progress, conducive for serious academic activities, learning/reading.

However, the study revealed problems encountered by undergraduate students in using the academic library such as inadequate reference sources, poor library staff/user relationship and lack of current and relevant materials. Others are inadequate funding, inadequate reading space and erratic power supply.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The University authorities should ensure proper funding of the university library.
2. The staff should possess good human relationship that will promote and encourage users' patronage of the library resources and services.
3. Provision should be made for a stand by generator to augment erratic power supply recently experienced in the country.
4. Recent reference materials/resources should be acquired to up-date the obsolete ones now available in the library.

REFERENCES

- Adeoye, M. O. and Popoola, S. O. (2011). Teaching effectiveness, availability, accessibility and use of library and information resources among teaching staff of schools of nursing in Osun and Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved Dec. 26, 2014 from www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/adeoye-popoola.htm
- Aguolu C.C.. & Aguolu, I.E. (2002). *Librarians and information management in Nigeria*.

Maiduguri: Ed- Linform Services.

- Aina, L. O. (2004). *Library and Information Science Text for Africa*. Ibadan: Third World Information Services.
- Ajala, I. O. (1997). Use of the university of Ibadan library resources by graduate student. *Library Review*, 46(5&6): 421-427.
- Ajayi NA, Adetayo J.O (2005). use of library book to enhance academic excellence in Nigeria tertiary institutions: A case study of Hezekiah Oluwasanni library. *J. Soc. Sci. 10* (2): 119-122.
- Akinade SO (2003). Patterns of first year students' use of a university Library: A survey at University of Ibadan. *Lagos J. Libr. Infor. sci.* 1: 22-26
- Akinade, J.O. 2003. Nigerian Medical Libraries: Challenges for the 21s'l century. *Nigerian Libraries*, 34 (1):46-54.
- Aloh, I. L. (1988). The role of library in functional literacy education in the society. *The Nation Builder*, 51
- Ani, O. E., Esin, J.E. & Edem, N. (2005): Adoption of information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Academic Libraries: a strategy for Library networking in Nigeria. *The Electronic Library Journal*, 23 (6), 27-37.
- Aniekwu, A.N and Ogbeide, F.N. (2002): Information Technology and Technological Development in Africa. In Yusufu, A.K. (ed) *Journal of Engineering Science and Applications (JESA)*. Faculty of Engineering and Technology, AAU, Ekpoma. 3 (2), 83pp.
- Anunobi, C.V. (2005): ICT Availability and use in Nigerian University Libraries. *Global Review of Library and Information Science*.1 (1), 39-51
- Barik, N. (2013). Assessing the effectiveness and usage of library resources and services of Einstein Academy of Technology and Management, Bhubaneswar: A faculty oriented study. *International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology*, 3(3): 171-175
- Bassey B.A (2006). User satisfaction with services in the academic libraries in cross river state: A comparative study. *Gateway lib. Journal*. 9: 21-29
- Bryson, J. (1990): *Effective Library and information Center Management*. England: Gower Publishing. 165pp
- Buckland, M. K. (1999). Library services and their users as a system. Retrieved Dec. 25, 2014, from <http://sunsite.berkeley.edu/Literature/Services/chapter4.html>
- Chisenga, J. (1995): The Skills of Information Technology in Zambian Libraries. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*. 5(1)19-24 pp
- Cohn, Z. and Lefolli, S. (1995): *Dictionary of Information Technology*. London:Claremont Books. 75pp.
- Ebijuwa, A.S. (2005): Information and communication technology in university libraries: the Nigerian experience. *Communicate, Journal Of Library and Information Science*, 7 (1&2).
- Edoka, B.E. (2000). Introduction to library science, Onitsha, Palma Publishing and Links Company 14-15p.
- Ehikhamenor, F.A.(1993): Information Technology and scientific and technological information in Nigeria: revolution and evolution". *Africa Journal Of Library, Archives And Information Science*. 39 (2) 113-123

- Elaturoti, D.F. (1993). Usage pattern of library resources among secondary school students: users survey of Abadina Media Resources Center. *Nigeria School Library Journal* 3 (122) p.30.
- Eyitayo, S.A. (1998): *Relevance Of The New Information Technologies In Cataloguing*. A paper presented at the Annual Cataloguing and Classification Seminar/Workshop, Ilorin (25th-30th October).
- Fayose, P.O. (1995). *School Library Resources Center for Educational excellence*. Ibadan: Federal Ministry of Education p.13.
- Harvey, L. (2004). *Analytic Quality Glossary*, Quarterly Research International. <http://www.qualityresearchinternational.com/glossary/>
<http://www.libunicletu/science/instruction/glossary.html> Retrieved on the 14th November 2009.
- Idowu, A.O. and Mabawonku, I. (1999): Information technology facilities application in some Nigeria Research and University Libraries. *Africa Journal of Library, Archives And Information Science*. 9(1). 27-36.
- IFLA Principles for the Care and Handling of Library Materials (2010). International Preservation Issues, Number One. (Internet) Retrieved from <http://archive.ifla.org/VI/news/pchlm.pdf>. 26th July, 2015
- Igun SE, Adogbeji O B 2007. "Study habits of postgraduate students in selected Nigerian Universities, Library Philosophy and Practice. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.uni.edu/libphi/prac/153>.
- Iyanda D. F., & Salawu A.K. (2006). *Library education for higher institutions*. Remi Osarayi & Sons Ents. Osogbo.
- Jaiyeola, R. (2007): Information and Communication (ICT) as a tool for Chartered Accountants. *The National Accountant*. 46 (1), 48 – 49pp.
- Nok, G. (2006). The challenge of computerising a university library in Nigeria: The case of Kashim Ibrahim Library, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* 8.2. Retrieved Dec. 25, 2014, from <http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu>
- Nwalo, K. I. N. (2000): Managing Information for Development in the 21st Century: prospects for African libraries, challenges to the world. *Booklet 8. IFLA Jerusalem*. 14p
- Nwokedi, V.C. (2007): Impact of Internet Use in Teaching and Research Activities of the Academic Staff of the Faculty of Medical Science. University of Jos. A case Study. *Gateway Library Journal*, 10 (1), 23-33.
- Odion , F. and Adetona, C.O. (2009): Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a tool for effective performance by Academic Librarians in Edo State of Nigeria. *Communicate, Journal of Library and information Science*. 11(1), 27-31
- Ojedokun AA (2007). *Information Literacy for Tertiary Education Students in Africa*. Ibadan: Third Word Information Services Limited.
- Ojedokun, A. A. (2000): Prospects of Digital Libraries. *African Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science*. 10(1). 13 –21.
- Oketunji, I. (2001): Computer Application to Libraries. *In a Compendium of Papers presented at the 39th National Annual Conference and AGM of the NLA*, Owerri. 2 –14
- Oketunji, I.(2000): Application of information technologies in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects; paper presented at the *10th Biennial Conference of the National Association of Library and Information Science Educators*. 7-20

- Okiy R B (2000). Assessing students and faculty use of academic libraries in Nigeria. The study of Delta State University Abrarka. *Frontiers of information and information science* 2(2): 96-101
- Olofinsawe AA, Oyeniyi DA (2010). Students use of the school libraries: a case study of Federal University of Technology Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Owena J. Lib. Inform. Sci.* 3:65-72.
- Onuoha, U. D., Omokoje, A. and Bamidele, I. A. (2013). Assessing service effectiveness and satisfaction with library services at Babcock University, Nigeria. *Information and Knowledge Management*. Vol. 3 (9). Retrieved Dec. 26, 2014 from www.iiste.org
- Osinulu LF (1998). Library use in Ogun State University, *Gateway Library Journal* 1:81-87.
- Oyesiku FA, Oduwole AA (2004). Use of an academic library: a survey on the Olabisi Onabanjo University Libraries. *Lagos J. Inform. Sci.* 2:96-101
- Oyewumi, O. O. (2006). Effective utilization of school libraries in some selected secondary schools in Ogbomosho North local government, Oyo State. *Language and Librarianship Journal* 2(1): 66-75
- Ozoemelem OA (2000). Use of electronic resources by post graduate students of the department of Library and Information Science of Delta state university, Abraka, Nigeria, Retrieved from
- Patra, B.k.(2008) The Role Of Information and Communication Technology on Management and Services Of Academic Libraries. *Techno India Group Research Journal*, 1(1).
- Pillow, A. (2003): Database Electronic Resources
- Poll, R. (2004). Quality. IFLA 2004 (Presentation). Available at: [http://www.ulb.immuenster.de/projektel/outcome/downloads/IFLA% 20 2004-quality.Ppt](http://www.ulb.immuenster.de/projektel/outcome/downloads/IFLA%202004-quality.Ppt)
- Rana, H.K. (2009): *Impact of Information and Communication Technology on Academic Libraries in Punjab*. Source: <http://www.goarticles.com/cgi-bin/showa/cgi? =1239032> Retrieved 28/08/2009
- Reitz, J.M. 2004. Dictionary for library and information science, London: Libraries Unlimited. 788p.
- Roberson, J.W. (2005). *Internet Use among African-America Collage Students: An Exploratory Study*. Poo Quest Database. Retrieved May 12, 2006.
- Roberson, T.J., Applin, M.B. and Schweinle, W., (2005). School libraries' impact upon student achievement and school professionals' attitudes that influence use of library programs. *Research for Educational Reform*, 10(1), pp. 45-52.
- Tsafe AG 2004. Students' utilization of Usaman Danfodio university medical library, Sokoto Gateway Lib .J. 7:10 – 20.
- Ubogu, F. N. (2000): The Paperless Society: Farce or Reality. *African Journal Of Library And, Archives And Information Science*. 10(1), 13 – 21.
- Ugah AD (2007). Evaluating the use of university libraries in Nigeria: A case study of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. *Library Philosophy and practice*, 2007
- Ugah, A. D. (2011). Staff and quality of information sources and the use of library services in a university library. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved Dec. 26, 2014 from www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/ugah8.htm
- Akpan, B. B., Agam, B. M., & Bassey, S. A. (2018). The Future of E-books in Our Contemporary World. *Journal of Advances in Library and Information Science*, 7(3),

246-249.

Akpan, B. B., & Akpan, B. S. (2018). Intellectual Freedom and Censorship. *Journal of Advancements in Library Sciences*, 5(1), 33-40.

QUESTIONNAIRE ON THE SURVEY OF STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF EKITI STATE UNIVERSITY LIBRARY SERVICES AND RESOURCES

Dear Respondent,

I am a final year student in the department of library, archival and information studies, University of Ibadan, carrying out a study **the survey of students perception of Ekiti State University library services and resources**. I therefore solicit for your honest response as information provided is purely for academic purposes and will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

BAMIGBOYE OMOLOLA MERCY

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. Name _____ of _____ Faculty/Department.....
2. Gender (a) Male [] (b) Female []
3. Age Group 12-16 () 17-21 () 22-26 () 27-31 () 32 and above []
4. Religion: Christianity () Islam () Others.....
5. What _____ is _____ your _____ discipline?
.....
6. What is your level (a) 100 [] (b) 200 [] (c) 300 [] (d) 400 []

SECTION B: PURPOSES AND FREQUENCY OF USE OF THE LIBRARY

7. How often do you make use of the library? Daily [], Weekly [], Monthly [], Occasionally []

8. For what purpose(s) do you make use of the library?

- For assignment [] * For reading magazines and newspapers []
- For examination [] * For leisure and recreation
- Others, please specify _____

7. What are the types of Library resources in the academic library? Please tick using this scale: VRA: Very Readily Available, RA: Readily Available, NRA: Not Readily Available, NA: Not Available

Library resources	VRA(4)	RA(3)	NRA(2)	NA(1)
Dictionary				
Encyclopedia				
Internet facilities				
Abstracts				

Yearbooks				
Atlases				
Gazettes				
CD-ROM				
Computer/printers				
Gazetteers				
Journals				
Almanacs				
Online public access catalogue				
Maps				
Law reports				
Books				

8. Please assess the availability of the following library services VRA: Very Readily Available, RA: Readily Available, NRA: Not Readily Available, NA: Not Available

Library services	VRA(4)	RA(3)	NRA(2)	NA(1)
Active Dissemination of Information(SDI)				
Library loan/cooperation				
Current Awareness Services (CAS)				
Indexing & abstracting services				
Answering of users' queries				
Library education i.e. teaching users how best to exploit library resources				
Library display and publicity				
Internet facilities				
Photocopying services				
Reference services				
Mail services				
Telephone services				
Online public access catalogue (OPAC)				

How do you perceive the academic library? Please tick as follows SA: Strongly, A: Agree, D: Disagree, SD: Strongly Disagree

PERCEPTION OF ACADEMIC LIBRARY SERVICE AND RESOURCES	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)
The library is a place for serious academic activities				
The library is useful to my academic progress				
It is conducive enough for learning and reading				
The library resources and useful and up-to-date				
Librarians in he library are friendly and knowledgeable.				
The resources are adequate and up-to-date				
Librarians answer my users queried timely and adequately.				
Librarians encourage students to read and study				
The environment is conducive for reading				
Librarian lack good interpersonal relationship				

To what extent do you think the following challenges affect your library in supporting learning?
 SA: Strongly, A: Agree, D: Disagree, SD: Strongly Disagree

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED	SA(4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)
Inadequate library funding				
Poor library staff/user relationship				
Inadequate reference sources				
Erratic power supply				
Lack of current and relevant materials				
Inadequate reading space				
Lack of ICT resources (Internet)				
Inadequate staff strength				

Any suggestion please feel free to do so